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Formulating Nursing Diagnoses and Developing Care Plans

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the formulation of nursing diagnoses and the development of care plans within the nursing process. The study relies on secondary sources of data collected from textbooks, journal articles, nursing periodicals and internet sourced materials which were complemented with case studies of medical cases including the observations from nursing practices. The results of the review emphasize the role of assessment in identifying patient needs and outline the use of subjective and objective data in clinical judgment. The types of nursing diagnoses as defined by North American Nursing Diagnosis Association-I, the integration of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs in prioritizing care, and the PES format for diagnostic statements were examined. A case study illustrates the practical application of these concepts in managing chronic renal failure. The results from the review underscore the importance of standardized diagnostic language and individualized care planning in enhancing patient outcomes and professional nursing practice.

Keywords: nursing diagnosis; nursing process; patient assessment; care plan; clinical judgment, nursing interventions; geriatric care

INTRODUCTION

The nursing process is a systematic approach to delivering patient care, and nursing diagnosis plays a pivotal role in guiding interventions and outcomes. This paper explores the formulation of nursing diagnoses and the development of care plans, emphasizing assessment, classification, and practical application.

Nursing process functions as a systematic guide to client-centred care and guides the nurse to individualize, contextualize and prioritize problem areas. The steps consist of assessment, nursing diagnosis, outcome identification, planning, intervention and evaluation. Nursing diagnosis is the second step of the six (6) sequential steps in the nursing process (Tammy, 2021)

Assessment, the first step in nursing process, is the collection and interpretation of data and it is an essential component of the nursing process which assists in the nursing diagnosis. There are two components to a comprehensive nursing assessment. The first component is a systematic collection of subjective (described by the patient) and objective (observed by the nurse) assessment data. It is done by taking a nursing health history and examining the patient. The second component of the nursing assessment is an analysis of the data and its use in a meaningful way to formulate an easily understandable and precise nursing care plan. One way this can be done is by making use of nursing diagnoses to plan and evaluate patient-centred outcomes and associated nursing interventions. (Brenda, 2014)

Data to be collected during assessment can be primary or secondary. At interview, verifiable data from the primary source (patient) and secondary sources (family, healthcare professionals, medical records) are elicited. Nursing health history include biographical information, reasons for seeking

healthcare, patient expectations, present illness or health concerns, health, family, environmental, and psychosocial history, spiritual health, history of allergies, dietary restrictions, relevant medical history. Physical examination includes vital signs records, other objective measurements made, e.g. height, weight, sputum, cough, diaphoresis Examination of all body systems in a systematic manner (Patt, et al., 2009).

Data from nursing assessments are necessary to identify problems in the order of clinical significance at a specific time and according to the urgent need for nursing interventions.

UNDERSTANDING NURSING DIAGNOSIS

According to North American Nursing Diagnosis Association (NANDA) International (2021), a nursing diagnosis is a clinical judgment about individual, family, or community responses to actual or potential health problems or life processes. It provides the foundation for selecting nursing interventions to achieve outcomes for which nurses are accountable.

According to Gordon (2008) assessment data are used in the three types of professional judgment within the nursing process:

1. **Diagnostic judgement:** identification of an actual problem or potential health problem
2. **Therapeutic judgement:** decisions about intervention, outcome projection and evaluation
3. **Ethical judgement:** identification of an actual problem or potential moral problem

Health care professionals face complex decisions daily regarding patient care— and must do so with decreased resources. What is the area of concern that nurses can treat/prevent/monitor? (*Diagnosis*). What is an appropriate goal for this patient? (*Outcome*). What treatment is most effective? (*Intervention*) (NANDA, 2007).

Clinical judgment is an important nursing skill in this process because it enables an accurate identification of the nursing diagnosis (Brenda, 2014).

DEFINITION OF NURSING DIAGNOSIS

Nursing diagnosis is a clinical judgment about individual, family, or community responses to actual or potential health problems/life processes. Nursing diagnosis provides the basis for selection of nursing interventions to achieve outcomes for which the nurse is accountable [North American Nursing Diagnosis Association (NANDA), 2021].

Nursing diagnosis are the logical culmination of the analysis of the assessment data. They include a description of the functional behaviours that can be improved through nursing interventions and the causative factors of those aspects of patient behaviour that nurses need to improve or influence (Patt, et al., 2009).

TYPES OF NURSING DIAGNOSIS

The North American Nursing Diagnosis Association-International (NANDA-International), provision is made for four categories of diagnosis:

- i. Actual (Problem-Focused)
- ii. Risk
- iii. Health Promotion
- iv. Syndrome.

Summary of NANDA 2020 – 2023 Edition

235 diagnoses

- 25 new
- 13 revised
- 7 retired
- 13 Domains
- 47 Classes

The Domains

1. Health Promotion
2. Nutrition
3. Elimination/Exchange
4. Activity/Rest

- 5.
6. Self-perception
7. Role Relationships
8. Sexuality
9. Coping/Stress Tolerance
10. Life Principles
11. Safety/ Protection
12. Comfort
13. Growth/Development

There is difference between Nursing Diagnosis and Medical Diagnosis. The differences are illustrated in the Table 1:

Table 1: Difference between Nursing Diagnosis and Medical Diagnosis

S/N	Nursing Diagnosis	Medical Diagnosis
1.	Within the scope of nursing practice	Within the scope of medical practice
2.	Identify responses to health and illness	Focuses on curing pathology
3.	Can change from day to day	Stays the same as long as the disease is present

According to Lunney (2009), Nurses need knowledge of diagnoses, definitions and defining characteristics, especially those common to the populations with which they work and the diagnostic processes that are used to interpret patient data. Skills of analyzing, logical reasoning, and applying standards are thinking processes required for accurate diagnosis in nursing. These skills are developed through:

- Discussions of how data should be clustered to generate accurate diagnoses
- Relation of data clusters to diagnoses
- Comparisons of existing data to expected data based on research findings.

MASLOW'S HIERARCHY OF NEEDS

A nursing diagnosis encompasses Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs and helps to prioritize and plan care based on patient-centred outcomes. In 1943, Abraham Maslow developed a hierarchy based on basic fundamental needs innate for all individuals. Basic physiological needs/goals must be met before higher needs/goals can be achieved such as self-esteem and self-actualization. Physiological and safety needs provide the basis for the implementation of nursing care and nursing interventions. Thus, they are at the base of Maslow's pyramid, laying the foundation for physical and emotional health (Shih et al., 2018 and Maslow, et al., 2008).

Figure 1: Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

- 1. Basic Physiological needs:** Nutrition (water and food), elimination (Toileting), airway (suction)-breathing (oxygen)-circulation (pulse, cardiac monitor, blood pressure) (ABC's), sleep, sex, shelter, and exercise.
- 2. Safety and Security:** Injury prevention (side rails, call lights, hand hygiene, isolation, suicide precautions, fall precautions, car seats, helmets, seat belts), fostering a climate of trust and safety (therapeutic relationship), patient education (modifiable risk factors for stroke, heart disease).
- 3. Love and Belonging:** Foster supportive relationships, methods to avoid social isolation (bullying), employ active listening techniques, therapeutic communication, sexual intimacy.
- 4. Self-Esteem:** Acceptance in the community, workforce, personal achievement, sense of control or empowerment, accepting one's physical appearance or body habitus.
- 5. Self-Actualization:** Empowering environment, spiritual growth, ability to recognize the point of view of others, reaching one's maximum potential.

FORMULATING OF NURSING DIAGNOSIS

The formulation of a nursing diagnosis by employing clinical judgment assists in the planning and implementation of patient care (Tammy, et al., 2021). Identifying nursing diagnoses and prioritizing these problem areas are the major intended process outcomes (Brenda, 2014).

Formulating a nursing diagnosis on the basis of a patient's situation and health is a task that places great demands on a nurse's skills in many areas. The nurses are motivated in their work with nursing diagnoses as they clarify the individual needs of the patient. A nursing diagnosis helps nurses to see the patient in a holistic perspective, which facilitates the decision of specific nursing interventions. The use of nursing diagnoses can lead to greater quality and patient safety and may increase nurses' awareness of nursing and strengthen their professional role (Hakans, 2012).

There are two ways to formulate a nursing diagnosis. A two-part system consists of the *nursing diagnosis* and the *related to* statement, with the latter listing those aetiological factors relevant to the diagnosis. A three-part system, known as the PES (problem–etiology–symptoms) system (Table 2), includes the above, plus a statement of the *defining characteristics* which are the various signs and symptoms identified during the nursing assessment and used to make the diagnosis.

Table 2: Three-part PES diagnostic statement

P (Problem)	E (Etiology)	S (Symptoms)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The client's response to a problem. - The nursing diagnosis (label); a concise term or phrase that represents a pattern of related cues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What's causing/ contributing to the client's problem? - The related to factors, i.e. the related causes or contributor to the problem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What's the evidence of the problem? - Defining characteristics statement, summarizing symptoms identified during the nursing assessment

Adapted from Robert, et al., (2009)

Cues are analyzed in relation to possible diagnoses. Existing cues are matched with the expected cues for the diagnoses being considered. During the evaluation of cues and related diagnoses, nurses may decide that there are not enough data to make a diagnostic decision that there is enough evidence for one or more likely diagnoses. If there are not enough data to make a diagnosis, then the next step involves a focused search for additional cues. If there is enough supporting evidence, a diagnosis is made and then validated (NANDA, 2007).

The formulation of a nursing diagnosis as a standardized statement for expressing the results of the assessment of the problems and needs of a patient provides a uniform way of identifying, describing, focusing on, and dealing with the problems and needs and is an ideal framework on which to base the nursing process. Once identified and documented, the nursing diagnosis provides direction for the remainder of the nursing process. Today, standardized nursing diagnostic statements continue to evolve into dynamic conceptual systems that guide the classification of nursing diagnoses into a widely used international one. By using nursing diagnoses and standardized descriptions of nursing

interventions and patient outcomes, nurses around the world are enabled to use the same language to systematically document their work with patients, families, and communities.

Figure 2: Correct Diagnostic Process

Figure 3: Incorrect Diagnostic Process

Example of Formulating of Diagnosis

A patient with active pulmonary TB could be *diagnosed* with hyperthermia *related* to infection, disease, dehydration, and an increased metabolic rate and with *defining characteristics* including fever (core body temperature elevated at least 0.8–1.1°C) above the person’s normal temperature (>

38°C), or hyperthermia (body temperature > 40°C) with flushed or hot skin, increased respiratory rate, and tachycardia

WRITING CARE PLANS

The nursing care plan incorporates specific nursing interventions and activities to treat specific nursing diagnoses or deal with problem areas such as changes in food intake, impaired capacity for personal care, risk for accidental injuries due to general weakness and mild dementia, grief unrelated to the health problem and other needs of the geriatric patient and the caregiver. Included in the plan are nursing actions to ensure the continuity of all prescribed medical treatments and other intervention modalities for the geriatric patient (Brenda, 2014).

A nursing care plan outlines the nursing care to be provided to an individual/ family/ community. It is a set of actions the nurse will implement to resolve/support nursing diagnoses identified by nursing assessment. The creation of the plan is an intermediate stage of the nursing process. It guides in the on-going provision of nursing care and assists in the evaluation of that care.

The following are characteristics of Nursing Care Plan

- Its focus is holistic, and is based on the clinical judgment of the nurse, using assessment data collected from a nursing framework.
- It is based upon identifiable nursing diagnoses
- It focuses on client-specific nursing outcomes that are realistic for the care recipient
- It includes nursing interventions which are focused on the etiologic or risk factors of the identified nursing diagnoses.
- It is a product of a deliberate systematic process.
- It relates to the future

There two (2) types of formal nursing care plan, namely:

- a) **Individualized care plan:** tailored to meet the unique need of a specific client.
- b) **Standardized care plan:** specifies nursing care for group of clients with common needs. E.g SNCP for all clients with pneumonia

According to Vera (2021), the following are steps for writing nursing care plan

Step 1: Data Collection or Assessment

Step 2: Data Analysis and Organization

Step 3: Formulating Your Nursing Diagnoses

Step 4: Setting Priorities

Step 5: Establishing Client Goals and Desired Outcomes

Short Term and Long Term Goals

Components of Goals and Desired Outcomes

Step 6: Selecting Nursing Interventions

Types of Nursing Interventions

Step 7: Providing Rationale

Step 8: Evaluation

Step 9: Putting it on Paper

Case Study

The use of a nursing care plan is best illustrated by a case study.

Table 3 : Nursing Care Plan of Mr Kada Maza with Chronic Renal Failure

NURSING DIAGNOSIS	NURSING OBJECTIVE	NURSING INTERVENTION	SCIENTIFIC PRINCIPLES	OUTCOME OF CARE	EVALUATION	SIGN
Fluid volume excess related to Kidney failure as evidence by swelling of the face, abdomen, limbs.	<p>Goal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintenance of ideal body weight without excess fluid <p>Expected Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demonstrate no rapid weight changes - Maintains dietary and fluid restriction - Exhibit normal skin turgor without edema - Exhibit normal vital signs - Exhibit no neck vein distention - Decrease thirst - Decrease dryness of oral Mucous membrane 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Daily weigh - Assess intake and output - Assess skin turgor and presence of edema - Assess neck vein for distention - Assess BP and respiratory rate and rhythm to provide baseline data - Assess fluid used to take medication - Assist patient to cope with his disease 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Will give clear picture of progress or otherwise. 2. Intake and output chart will monitor improvement status of the patient 3. Absence of Neck vein distention will give us sign of good progress of the patient 4. Normal BP shows sign of improvement in renal failure. 5. Improvement in respiratory rate is an evidence of progress. 6. It will limit intake as per instruction. 	All planned care were carried out with full cooperation of the patient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patient stated normal urine output (more than 400) - BP decreased - Ideal body weight is maintained - No neck vein distended - No edema 	

CONCLUSION

Formulating nursing diagnoses and developing care plans follows the nursing process, beginning with Assessment (data collection), then Diagnosis (identifying health problems using NANDA guidelines), followed by Planning (setting goals and interventions), Implementation (carrying out the interventions), and Evaluation (assessing effectiveness and making adjustments). A nursing diagnosis is a clinical judgment about a human response to a health condition or vulnerability, and the care plan provides a structured, patient-centred framework for addressing those needs. The entire process is iterative, meaning it can be revisited and revised as the patient's condition changes, making it a dynamic and critical tool for holistic patient care.

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